

Seeding Change:

Transforming Seed Access in Uganda through Social and Behavior Change Interventions

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Key Messages

- Social norms and institutions play a critical role in the production and adoption of improved seeds by shaping the behaviors and expectations of individuals and communities involved in agriculture.
- Gender inequity, prevailing myths, and misinformation about improved rice seeds dissuade farmers from adopting them and limit women's access to seeds.
- Ensuring equitable access to quality seeds for all farmers is critical in boosting Uganda's agricultural productivity. This can be addressed by improving farmer knowledge and trust in improved varieties and creating supportive policies and programs that lower smallholder farmers' economic and social barriers.
- A holistic approach that integrates economic viability and the promotion of gender equity is critical to farming communities' overall economic growth and resilience. By focusing on the economic empowerment of women farmers while simultaneously addressing gender disparities in access to resources and decision-making, interventions can create a more enabling environment for all farmers.
- The social and behavior change communication intervention highlights women's productive potential, their significant contributions to food output, and the need for equal access to resources and services to maximize agricultural productivity.
- Challenging gender norms in Uganda's agricultural sector requires a multifaceted approach that addresses women's empowerment and broader socioeconomic challenges and promotes inclusivity.

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Rice production in Uganda

Rice productivity in Uganda remains low at an estimated 2.5 metric tons per hectare which is dominated by smallholder farmers who primarily produce for sale, followed by household consumption (Akongo et al., 2017). Annual rice production in Uganda was at 730,000 metric tons in 2022, 727,000 metric tons in 2021, and 373,000 metric tons in 2020 (FAOSTAT, 2023), showing a declining trend.

Smallholder farmers in Uganda's Eastern, Northern, and Midwestern regions produce over 90% of the rice under either rainfed or irrigated conditions (Alibu et al., 2016), and on average, women represent 56% of the agricultural labor force. However, women generally often encounter barriers, including limited access to land, credit, and education opportunities, which hinder their full participation and potential productivity and contribute to the gender gap within the agriculture sector.

The rural economy's gendered character represents a significant barrier to economic growth and poverty reduction. The sector's productivity potential is not fully realized when women are not given equal access to resources and opportunities in agriculture. Thus, addressing the gender disparities in agriculture is not only a matter of equity but also a strategic economic priority that can lead to more robust and inclusive growth. Studies have shown that closing the agricultural gender gap could significantly improve productivity. For instance, eliminating the gap between men and women in access to agricultural resources could raise yields on women's farms by 20-30% and potentially increase overall agricultural production in developing countries by 2.5-4% (UN Women et al., 2015; UN Women and UNDP-UNEP PEI 2018).

Key barriers to the adoption of seeds of new varieties

The major reason for low rice yields is smallholder farmers' underuse of yield-boosting resources like high-quality seeds, fertilizers, and herbicides and support from agricultural extension offices. Additional factors affecting rice production include sparse investment in irrigation systems, lack of proper agricultural financing, limited use of farm machinery, and substandard practices in handling crops after harvest, leading to poor grain quality.

The Uganda National Rice Development Strategy from 2009 attributes these issues to a range of policy shortcomings related to agricultural inputs and financing, inadequate policy enforcement regarding soil and water management, weak farmer organizations, and insufficient funding. Also noted are a pervasive lack of motivation, minimal support for local extension workers, and a dearth of rice-specific expertise among those workers (Nanyonjo & Nchanji, 2023). Other notable difficulties facing the rice sector involve pest and disease management, a lack of suitable technologies for drying and threshing rice, and a general shortfall in rice farming knowledge within the farmer communities.

Apart from the above challenges, traditional gender roles, lack of information, and resistance to change also contribute to gender disparity and hinder the overall development of the rice agricultural sector in Uganda (Marimo et al., 2021).

Shifting Norms, Improving Adoption and Utilization of Improved Seeds

Promoting the adoption of improved seeds among farmers involves a comprehensive approach that addresses individual factors of knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs, as well as gender norms and structural barriers that affect access to equitable resources, support systems, and innovative agricultural technologies. Recognizing and addressing these multifaceted impacts of individual, institutional, and social factors among rural communities can pave the way for sustainable and inclusive agricultural development. This approach requires not only recognizing the gender disparities in access to resources but also challenging and transforming the underlying social norms that perpetuate inequality. Collaboration among all key stakeholders, including policymakers, agricultural extension services, and local communities, is required to develop targeted interventions that address gender disparities in access to resources and support systems while promoting community engagement and effective behavior change interventions.

Communication regarding social and behavioral change is crucial in promoting and adopting new agricultural practices and technologies. Through targeted communication campaigns, training programs, and community engagement activities, smallholder farmers can be empowered to renegotiate gender and social

influencing behavior and practices around access, adoption, production of improved seed, and overall socioeconomic development.

To implement evidence-based social and behavior change (SBC) strategies for seed information and seed entrepreneurship for unreached, smallholder women and young farmers in Butaleja District, Eastern Uganda, the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) and the Alliance of Bioversity International and CIAT (ABC), under Work Package 6 of the Seed Equal Initiatives in collaboration with the Centre for Behaviour Change and Communication (CBCC), conducted a baseline assessment study to determine the barriers and facilitators of equitable seed access and constraining gender and social norms among the unreached smallholder farmers in the selected county.

The baseline findings revealed poor or inadequate knowledge of new seeds of improved varieties and their adoption, especially among women. Further, it was identified that women have difficulty accessing agricultural inputs like seeds, credits, and land. Because of this, women find it difficult to enter and participate in seed distribution channels, which is also why they lack access to training, seed fairs, trials, and farm demonstrations. Information about improved rice varieties becomes diluted by the time women hear about them because extension workers expect the heads of the households, who are usually men, to share seed information with the women in their respective households.

These findings informed the content and design of the SBC strategies, aiming to empower smallholder farmers, women, and youth, enhance seed access and utilization, and contribute to increased agricultural productivity, livelihoods, and food security in Butaleja District and beyond.

Engendering equitable access to and adoption of improved seeds through social and behavioral change communication interventions

A workshop was organized to disseminate the baseline findings and develop social and behavior change strategies in a multi-sectorial, multi-disciplinary stakeholder setting in the Butaleja District. Local government executives, research institutions, private organizations, development partners, value chain actors, and smallholder farmers co-designed a social

behavior change strategy for seed production and entrepreneurship intervention.

Key behaviors that have the most significant impact on seed access and entrepreneurship were identified. Participants divided into different actor groups identified and prioritized behaviors relevant to each actor within the sector. The prioritized behavioral change includes:

- Engaging more women in entrepreneurship and skills training
- Changing mindset where women are included in decision-making and gender empowerment
- Creating linkages between researchers and extension officers with women in local seed business
- Registering and strengthening more women's groups
- Conducting cost-benefit analysis with potential seed producers
- Intensify awareness creation campaigns for farmers on the benefits of improved seed
- Training on behavior change so that some cultural norms do not become hindrances to development
- Report scarcity of grain to the relevant authorities and lobby for grain and seed subsidies
- Capacity building on nutrition and production.
- Branding of the grains and seeds
- Educating youth on local seed businesses
- Supporting youth to form groups so that they can hire land and access capital
- Bring in technologies to entice youth eg. Labour saving technologies
- Awareness creation for youth to see opportunities in Agribusiness
- The stakeholders reviewed the drafted SBC strategy based on the behavior prioritization activity.

Social and Behavioral Change Campaign's Message Development

The concept posters with pictures were critically analyzed by considering the look and feel of the presented materials to inform their appropriateness for use within Butaleja for the campaign. Below are sample posters finalised with input from stakeholders.

The campaign's messaging aims to foster an environment where farmers feel confident and equipped to try new agricultural practices, which is essential for influencing and reinforcing positive attitudes toward adopting improved seeds.

Engaging men, community leaders, research agencies, and other stakeholders as allies in discussions and initiatives is crucial in challenging gender norms. Motivating positive action through campaigns can inspire farmers and other actors to take action by emphasizing the tangible benefits that improved seeds can have on their livelihoods and the well-being of their communities.

- **Raising Awareness:** Clear and positive messages can effectively educate farmers about the benefits and drawbacks of new seed varieties, including higher yields, resistance to pests and diseases, and adaptability to climate change.
- **Shifting Perceptions:** Campaigns can help reframe perceptions of new seeds, presenting them as opportunities for growth and improvement rather than as unfamiliar risks.
- **Increasing Knowledge:** By providing information on where to obtain improved seeds, how to use them, and management practices, campaigns empower farmers with the knowledge they need to make informed decisions.
- **Changing Attitudes:** Positive messaging incorporating success stories and testimonials from other farmers can improve attitudes towards new seeds, making farmers more open to adopting them.
- **Creating Social Norms:** When positive messages highlight the widespread acceptance and success of improved seeds, this can create a new social norm, encouraging more farmers to adopt them as a standard practice.
- **Motivating Action:** Campaigns can inspire farmers to take action by emphasizing the tangible benefits improved seeds can have on their livelihoods and the well-being of their communities.

Mama, grow your future as a certified rice seed multiplier.

Help meet great demand for certified rice seeds as a multiplier for licensed cooperatives. Talk to your District Agricultural Officer to learn more.

Certified seed
E-no Sure

"Keep winning! Replace your old seed with new certified seed every few years."

Replanting seeds reduces yields and increases costs of managing pests and diseases. Available at your licensed local cooperative.

Certified seed
E-no Sure

- **Facilitating Support:** Positive campaigns can encourage the development of support systems, such as farmer groups or cooperatives, which can increase confidence in trying new seeds.

Campaign direction

Due to changing weather patterns, reduced rainfall, and an increase in pests and plant diseases, farming has become unpredictable. The farmer is uncertain if their crops will make it to maturity or whether the harvest will be plentiful. The off-taker is unsure of the quality of the grain or whether their buyers will appreciate it. The processor is uncertain if the market has a high demand for that grain or whether their clients will like the product.

For generations, farmers and other value chain actors have lived this uncertain way of life. It's time to reduce the uncertainty. The farmer needs to be confident that their crops will survive pests, diseases, and harsh weather and produce high yields. The off-taker needs to be confident that the grain he/she buys has matured well and is of high quality with no damage from pests and diseases. The processor needs to be confident that their grain is preferred by the market. The consumer needs to be confident that the grain he/she buys is highly nutritious and of good quality. Eno Sure means 'it's Sure'; in Uganda, young people use this phrase to iterate that something is 'legit' (genuine, authentic); and that's what we want the people of Butaleja to think when we talk about quality-improved seeds.

Policy Recommendations

Social and behavior change communication can raise awareness and create demand by addressing knowledge, information, motivation, and awareness gaps.

The ENO Sure Seed SBC Campaign was developed as a targeted information campaign that raised awareness and promoted the benefits of quality rice seeds. It applied and encouraged the use of media and community events to disseminate success stories. The campaign used local languages and culturally relevant channels to disseminate information that the target stakeholders could easily understand.

Normative change can effectively and carefully deconstruct and renegotiate sociocultural norms.

Mobilize and engage community influencers and leaders to endorse, model, and champion the adoption of improved seeds. Community dialogues can be organized to shift norms around gender and seed selection practices and address gender biases and constraints.

Government support through policymaking can help promote gender-sensitive seed public-private partnerships and seed distribution networks.

Governments can promote equitable environments for seed distribution by ensuring regulatory frameworks are gender-sensitive and needs-specific which can foster the same values in public-private partnerships that can support the development of seed distribution networks. Agricultural extension services should be cognizant of the needs of minorities and women farmers.

Establish economic and trade incentives to make seed and storage accessible to farmers.

Credit facilities and input subsidies for smallholder farmers are necessary to de-risk rice farmers, especially in the face of the effects of climate change. Such fiscal support must also implement a gender-sensitive approach to make sure that women can actively participate in seed distribution channels. Community-based seed banks can help improve seed access and storage at the local level, improving the production and yield of the farmers.

Organizing local leaders of diverse backgrounds can help encourage various stakeholders to adopt quality seeds and best practices in rice production.

Mobilizing local leaders and influencers to endorse and model the use of quality seeds can help spur insightful community discussions and address gender biases and constraints. Continuous assessment and balance of the diverse perspectives and potential impacts of strategies and technologies will be vital in developing comprehensive and sustainable approaches for rice production.

References

Doss, C. (2018). "Women and Agricultural Productivity: Reframing the Issues." *Development Policy Review* 36 (1): 35-50

Nanyonjo, G., & Nchanji, E. Seed credit model in Uganda": Participation and empowerment dynamics among smallholder women and men farmers. *Global Food Security*, 39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2023.100720>

Marimo, P.; Otieno, G.; Njuguna-Mungai, E.; Vernooy, R.; Halewood, M.; Fadda, C.; Mulumba, J.W.; Nyamongo, D.O.; Mollel, M (2021). The Role of Gender and Institutional Dynamics in Adapting Seed Systems to Climate Change: Case Studies from Kenya, Tanzania and Uganda. *Agriculture* 2021, 11, 840. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture11090840>.

McKenna, K. A. (2014). "The Role of Ugandan Women in Rural Agriculture and Food Security" *Electronic Theses and Dissertations*. 420. <https://digitalcommons.du.edu/etd/420>

UN Women, UNDP-UNEP PEI (United Nations Development Programme-United Nations Environment Programme Poverty-Environment Initiative) and World Bank. 2015. *The Cost of the Gender Gap in Agricultural Productivity in Malawi, Tanzania, and Uganda*. New York and Washington, DC: UN Women, UNDP, UNEP, and the World Bank Group.

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